

IMIDOCHLORIDES. PART VI.* CONDENSATION OF BENZANILIDE
IMIDOCHLORIDE WITH URETHANES. A NEW METHOD FOR
THE CONVERSION OF AROMATIC CARBOXYLIC ACIDS
INTO THE CORRESPONDING ALDEHYDES

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Benzanilide imidochloride has been condensed with phenylurethane and the resulting *N:N'*-diphenyl-*N'*-carbethoxybenzamidine, also obtained from *N:N'*-diphenylbenzamidine and chloro-carbonic ester, has been reduced by aluminium amalgam to the corresponding dihydro derivative. The reduced compound on hydrolysis by dilute acid readily affords benzaldehyde. This reaction provides a new and convenient method for the conversion of an aromatic carboxylic acid into the corresponding aldehyde through the stages: acid→anilide→amidine→*N*-carbethoxyamidine→dihydro compound→aldehyde. Similar results are obtained with *N*-methylurethane.

In continuation of the work by Shah and Ichaporia (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 431) who condensed benzanilide imidochloride with sodium derivative of urethanes and obtained *N*-phenyl-*N'*-carbethoxybenzamidine, which on subsequent cyclisation gave 4-hydroxy-2-phenylquinazoline, thus affording a novel synthesis of such quinazoline derivatives, benzanilide imidochloride (I) was condensed with sodium derivative of phenylurethane when *N:N'*-diphenyl-*N'*-carbethoxybenzamidine (II) was obtained. The constitution was established by its synthesis from *N:N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (III) and ethyl chloroformate. This condensation product (II), however, resisted all attempts at cyclisation to 2:3-diphenyl-3:4-dihydro-4-quinazolone (IV).

N:N'-Diphenyl-*N'*-carbethoxybenzamidine was found to be more stable than *N*-phenyl-*N'*-carbethoxybenzamidine. On hydrolysis it gave benzanilide. Action of bromine furnished a *dibromo* addition product, while in the case of *N*-phenyl-*N'*-carbethoxybenzamidine, benz-*p*-bromoanilide was obtained. With alcoholic potassium hydroxide it gave *N:N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (III) through hydrolysis and subsequent decarboxylation. On reduction *N:N'*-diphenyl-*N'*-carbethoxydihydrobenzamidine (VI) was obtained, which readily hydrolysed to benzaldehyde. This last reaction is an interesting observation as it affords a convenient method for the conversion of an aromatic carboxylic acid into the corresponding aldehyde. The acid may be converted through anilide into the imidochloride which can be condensed with sodium salt of phenylurethane and *N:N'*-diphenyl-*N'*-carbethoxy-acylamidine, thus obtained, be reduced to the corresponding dihydro compound which on hydrolysis would yield the aldehyde. Alternatively, *N:N'*-diaryl-*N'*-carbethoxy-acylamidine may be prepared by the action of chloro-carbonic ester on diarylbenzamidine which may be obtained through imidochloride from the anilide or directly by the condensation of anilide with aniline (Hoofmann, *Chem. Zentl.*, 1866, 161; cf. Sen and Ray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 646; Hill and Cox, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 3216; Shah and Sidiki, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1937, 6A, 132).

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Methylurethane, like phenylurethane, condensed with benzanilide imidochloride to give *N*-phenyl-*N'*-methyl-*N'*-carbethoxybenzamidine (VII). This also did not undergo ring-closure to furnish a quinazolone derivative. In general properties also, this benzamidine derivative behaved like its phenyl analogue and could be reduced to *N*-phenyl-*N'*-methyl-*N'*-carbethoxydihydrobenzamidine (V) which readily hydrolysed to benzaldehyde.

The above method of conversion essentially depends on the reduction of these *N'*-carbethoxybenzamidine derivatives to the dihydro compound. Merling (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 2064) observed that amidines derived from hydroaromatic acids could be reduced to a diphenylmethylenediamine base which on hydrolysis would yield the corresponding aldehyde. Sidiki and Shah (unpublished work) however, have noted that $-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ group in amidines, derived from aromatic acids, cannot be reduced to $-\text{CH}-\text{NH}-$ group. It would appear therefore that in the present case the reduction is made possible on account of the presence of the *N*-carbethoxy group.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Phenylurethane.—A solution of phenylurethane (26 g., 1.1 mol) in dry ether was added dropwise to a mixture of pulverised sodium (5 g., 1.1 atom) and dry ether and the mixture kept overnight when the sodium derivative separated. It was then refluxed with an ethereal solution of benzanilide imidochloride (30 g., 1 mol.) for 12 hours. Water was added to the ethereal solution, the ethereal layer dried and the ether removed. The residual red oil solidified on freezing. It was washed with light petroleum (65°-95°) and crystallised

from alcohol when *N:N'*-diphenyl-*N'*-carbethoxybenzamidine (II) separated in colorless rhombic prisms, m.p. 85-87°. (Found: N, 8.4. $C_{22}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8.1 per cent).

Synthesis of N:N'-diphenyl-N'-carbethoxybenzamidine from N:N'-diphenylbenzamidine (III) and Ethyl Chloroformate.—To a solution of *N:N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (Shah, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1924, 7, 205) (1 mol.) in dry benzene containing sodium bicarbonate (2.5 mol.) a benzene solution of ethyl chloroformate (1 mol.) was added with cooling in a freezing mixture. The yellow oil obtained on evaporation of the benzene solution was dissolved in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, then with water, and dried. On evaporation of ether a resinous mass was obtained which solidified on freezing. It was washed with light petroleum and crystallised from alcohol in prisms, m.p. 85-87°. This product on direct comparison was found to be identical with the above compound.

Reactions of N:N'-Diphenyl-N'-carbethoxybenzamidine

(1) *Attempts at cyclisation.*—The benzamidine, after prolonged heating at 250° was recovered unchanged. On distillation the *N*-carbethoxy group suffered hydrolysis and decarboxylation, and *N:N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (III), m.p. (after crystallisation from alcohol) and mixed m.p. 146°, was obtained. On treatment with phosphorus oxychloride for 3 hours at 120°-130° or with concentrated sulphuric acid for 20 hours at room temperature (30°), the original benzamidine was recovered, while with phosphorus pentoxide in xylene for 4 hours at 110°-120°, benzanilide, m.p. 158-60°, was formed.

(2) The benzamidine (2 g.) when heated with water at 150°-160° for 5 hours gave benzanilide, m.p. 160-61°. Unreacted benzamidine was recovered, when it was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid on a boiling water-bath for 15 minutes. With dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1, 20 c.c.) in a sealed tube at 120° for 5 hours benzoic acid, m.p. 120-21°, was obtained.

(3) The benzamidine (2 g.) on refluxing with alcoholic potassium hydroxide was hydrolysed and decarboxylated giving *N:N'*-diphenylbenzamidine, m.p. and mixed m.p. 144-46°.

(4) Bromine (0.3 g.) and the benzamidine (0.5 g.) in chloroform at room temperature gave a *dibromo addition product*, crystallised from nitrobenzene in yellow needles, m.p. 260-61°. (Found: Br, 31.5. $C_{22}H_{20}O_2N_2Br_2$ requires Br, 31.7 per cent).

(5) The benzamidine (2 g.) was refluxed with an excess of aluminium amalgam in moist ethereal solution for about 5 hours. The ethereal layer was dried, the ether removed and the product crystallised from a mixture of benzene and light petroleum when *N:N'*-diphenyl-*N'*-carbethoxydihydrobenzamidine (VI) separated in colorless, long needles, m.p. 104°-106°. (Found: N, 8.1. $C_{22}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8.1 per cent).

The dihydrobenzamidine (0.2 g.) when warmed with a little concentrated hydrochloric acid for a few minutes gave an oil. It was extracted with ether, the extract dried, and the ether removed. The residual oil was identified as benzaldehyde by preparing its phenylhydrazone, m.p. and mixed m.p. 158°.

Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Methylurethane—The sodium derivative of methylurethane (11.3 g.) in ether suspension was refluxed with an ethereal solution of benzanilide imidochloride (21.5 g.) for 5 hours. It was then diluted with

water, the ethereal layer dried, and the ether removed. The residual mass was extracted with chloroform, and the product obtained on removal of chloroform was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and light petroleum, when *N*-phenyl-*N'*-methyl-*N'*-carbethoxybenzamide separated in long rhombic needles, m.p. 90-92°. (Found: C, 72.5; H, 6.5; N, 10.0. $C_{17}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires C, 72.3; H, 6.4; N, 9.9 per cent).

Reactions.—(1) Attempts to cyclise the benzamide by heating it at 220°-240° or treatment with $POCl_3$ or concentrated sulphuric acid were unsuccessful. (2) On heating the benzamide with concentrated hydrochloric acid for 5 minutes on a water-bath, benzanilide, m.p. 160-61°, was formed. (3) Action of alcoholic potassium hydroxide furnished *N*-phenyl-*N'*-methylbenzamide, crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 130-32° (Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 2371; m.p. 130°); picrate, m.p. 167-69° (Pechmann, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 167-69°). (4) The benzamide (2 g.) was refluxed with an excess of aluminium amalgam in moist ether for 5 hours. The ether layer after drying and evaporation of ether gave *N*-phenyl-*N'*-methyl-*N'*-carbethoxydihydrobenzamide, crystallised from alcohol in prismatic needles, m.p. 166° (Found: C, 72.0; H, 7.0; N, 9.6. $C_{17}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires C, 71.8; H, 7.0; N, 9.8 per cent). The dihydrobenzamide on hydrolysis by warm concentrated hydrochloric acid gave benzaldehyde, isolated and characterised as in the previous case.